

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE CONCEPT OF PRIVACY IN THE LEGISLATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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Abstract. This article analyzes the guarantees of a person's right to privacy in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Foreign experiences related to this right have also been studied.

Keywords: Personal life, family secrets, citizenship, political rights, penal system, physical harassment, compulsory community service, judicial investigation activities, administrative punishment, compulsory community service, correctional work.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПОНЯТИЯ КОНФИДЕНЦИАЛЬНОСТИ В ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВЕ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН И ЗАРУБЕЖНЫХ СТРАН

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются гарантии права человека на неприкосновенность частной жизни в законодательстве Республики Узбекистан.

Изучался также зарубежный опыт, связанный с этим правом.

Ключевые слова: Личная жизнь, семейная тайна, гражданство, политические права, уголовно-исполнительная система, физическое притеснение, обязательные общественные работы, судебно-следственная деятельность, административное наказание, обязательные общественные работы, исправительные работы.

Private life is the physical and mental life of a physical person, free from external influences. Also, private life is family, household communication environment, religious attitude, non-work activities, personal interests and limited environments in this context, about which a person may request that information not be disclosed. For example, there are norms established in the legislation that the secret of adoption as a personal and family secret, the mutual life of a couple, as well as secret relationships with other people, even romantic relationships, should not be disclosed without the consent of the individual. Article 3 of the United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights adopted on December 10, 1948 states that everyone the right to privacy, and Article 12 states that no one can be arbitrarily interfered with in their private life, and that everyone has the right to be protected by law against such interference or aggression.

In addition, Article 17 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights states: "No one shall be entitled to arbitrary or unlawful interference with his private and family life, cannot be subjected to arbitrary or illegal encroachment on the privacy of his home or correspondence, or to illegal encroachment on his honor and dignity. Everyone has the right to be protected by law against such interference or aggression."

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, measures aimed at improving the organization of international obligations in the field of human rights and freedoms are being implemented consistently and step by step, in particular, measures aimed at creating the necessary organizational and legal conditions for the prevention of torture.

The accession of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the UN Convention against Torture on August 31, 1995 once again confirmed the state's aspirations to universally recognized values of human rights and freedoms. The recognition of a number of international standards regarding the observance of the rights of persons kept in prison has increased the attention of the state to the issues of bringing the system of punishment into line with international standards.

First of all, guarantees related to the right to privacy of a person are defined in Article 27 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and it is noted that everyone has the right to freedom and privacy.

Also, "On additional measures to strengthen the guarantees of citizens' rights and freedoms in judicial and investigative activities" Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 30, 2017 was an important event in the reform of the judiciary.

According to the decree, the use of torture, psychological and physical harassment and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment against participants in criminal proceedings or their close relatives in Uzbekistan, as evidence of any audio and video recordings and other materials obtained illegally within the criminal case use is strictly prohibited.

In addition, adopted on April 4, 2018 "On strengthening the guarantees of citizens' rights and freedoms in judicial investigation activities. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan" in connection with the adoption of measures, responsibility for torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment and punishment has been increased. The legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates the following punishments for violating the right to privacy.

According to Article 461 of the Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan, illegal collection or distribution of information about a person's personal life, which constitutes a personal or family secret, without his consent, is a basic calculation causes a fine from 10 times to 40 times of the amount.

If a person commits such an act again within 1 year after the administrative punishment for such an act is applied, it is now considered a crime.

According to Article 1411 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, administrative punishment is applied for illegal collection or distribution of information about a person's personal life, which constitutes a personal or family secret, without his consent. if it is committed later, it shall be punished with a fine of 50 to 100 times of the base calculation amount or compulsory community service for up to three hundred hours or correctional work for up to two years.

Nowadays, the number of users of Internet communication tools is increasing. As a result, there are many cases of data theft, disclosure of commercial secrets, interference in private life.

As a result of Internet spying on the personal information of famous people, inappropriate materials about them appear in the press and social networks.

Also, various applications running on special operating systems and "disguised" electronic programs aimed at collecting and processing personal data are being distributed. As a result of our citizens downloading photos, games, manuals, electronic documents, e-mails or other files, subscribers' contact list, incoming and outgoing call history, account passwords, bank account numbers are considered personal. , bank credit or debit card information and other information is

sent anonymously to the program author. As a result, if we do not take precautionary measures when telling others bank card number, PIN code, which are considered personal information, when sending copies of identity documents through social networks, we are considered to be the cause of disclosure of personal information.

Therefore, in order to prevent the disclosure of personal data, it is advisable to observe the following:

First, you should not send personal information through social networks.

Secondly, you should be careful about offers such as "high-income" work or "overseas inheritance".

Thirdly, one should not provide personal information when communicating with strangers through messengers, social networks, and various platforms.

Fourth, do not open suspicious files and applications, do not download information from unknown and suspicious sources, and do not open suspicious links.

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